

AID: An Automated Inclusivity-Bug Detector (GenderMag Supplemental documents)

ICSE 2021

[Author names omitted for blind review]

Table of content:

1. **GenderMag Forms:** Figure-1 (displayed on two pages) shows the Original GenderMag forms.
2. **Original Abi Persona (non customized Abi):** Figure-2 is the empty version of Abi. The blue lines are placeholders for custom information.
3. **Customized Abi persona:** Figure-3 shows the customized Abi persona used in this study. The blue text (background, age, occupation, etc.) are the customized portions.

All customizable personas, GenderMag forms, and instructions are available on <http://gendermag.org/>.

Scenario (Overall Goal):

Subgoal #__:

(e.g., See bookstore map.)

1. Will <persona> have formed this sub-goal as a step to their overall goal?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Maybe	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Which, if any, of <persona> facets did you use to answer the question?		
<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above	<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above	<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above
Why?	Why?	Why?

Action # ___:

(e.g., Tap 'Browse Off'.)

1a. [BEFORE ACTION] Will <persona> know what to do at this step? Why?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Maybe	<input type="checkbox"/> No
<i>Which, if any, of <persona> facets did you use to answer the question?</i>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above	<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above	<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above
Why?	Why?	Why?

1b. [AFTER ACTION] If <persona> does the right thing, will s/he know that s/he did the right thing and is making progress toward their goal? Why?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Maybe	<input type="checkbox"/> No
<i>Which, if any, of <persona> facets did you use to answer the question?</i>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above	<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above	<input type="checkbox"/> Motivations <input type="checkbox"/> Information Processing Style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Self-Efficacy <input type="checkbox"/> Attitude Towards Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above
Why?	Why?	Why?

Figure-1: Original GenderMag forms.

Abi (Abigail/Abishek)¹

- _____ years old
- Employed as a(n) _____
scanning all their emails first to get an overall picture before answering any of _____
- Lives in _____, _____, _____
_____ them.

Background and skills

_____ their software systems are new to Abi.
 _____ "numbers person" _____. Abi **likes Math** and knows how to think with
 numbers. _____
 Abi also **enjoys working with numbers and logic**. _____

Motivations and Attitudes

- **Motivations:** Abi uses technologies **to accomplish _____ tasks**, _____ learns new technologies if and when _____ needs to, but prefers to use methods _____ is **already familiar and comfortable with, to keep _____ focus** on the tasks _____ cares about.

- **Computer Self-Efficacy:** Abi has **lower self confidence than _____ peers about doing unfamiliar computing tasks**. If problems arise with _____ technology, _____ often **blames _____ for these problems**. This affects whether and how _____ will persevere with a task if technology problems have arisen.

- **Attitude toward Risk:** Abi's life is a little complicated and _____ **rarely has spare time**. So _____ is **risk averse about using unfamiliar technologies that might need _____ to spend extra time** on them, even if the new features might be relevant. _____ instead performs tasks using familiar features, because they're more predictable about what _____ will get from them and how much time they will take.

How Abi Works with Information and Learns:

- **Information Processing Style:** Abi tends towards a **comprehensive information processing style** when _____ needs to more information. So, instead of acting upon the first option that seems promising, _____ **gathers information comprehensively to try to form a complete understanding of the problem before trying to solve it**. Thus, _____ style is "burst-y"; first _____ reads a lot, then _____ acts on it in a batch of activity.

- **Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering:** When learning new technology, Abi leans toward **process-oriented learning**, e.g., tutorials, step-by-step processes, wizards, online how-to videos, etc., _____ **doesn't particularly like learning by tinkering with software** (i.e., just trying out new features or commands to see what they do), but when _____ does tinker, it has positive effects on _____ understanding of the software.

¹For distribution data on users similar to and different from Abi, see <http://gendermag.org/> for customizable versions including customizable pronouns.

Figure-2: Empty version of Abi. The blue lines are placeholders for custom information.

Abi (Abigail/Abishek)

- 28 Years Old
 - First-time contributor to OSS
 - Lives in Cardiff, Wales
- Abi has always liked music. When she is on her way to work in the morning, she listens to music that spans a wide variety of styles. But when she arrives at work, she turns it off, and begins her day by **scanning all her emails first to get an overall picture before answering any of them.** (This extra pass takes time but seems worth it.) Some nights she exercises or stretches, and sometimes she likes to play computer puzzle games like Sudoku.

Background and Skills

Abi works as an accountant. She is comfortable with the technologies she uses regularly, but she just moved to this employer 1 week ago, and **the software systems are new to her.**

Abi has never taken any computer programming or IT systems classes. She **likes Math** and knows how to think with numbers. She writes and edits spreadsheet formulas in her work.

In her free time, she also **enjoys working with numbers and logic,** she especially likes working out puzzles and puzzle games, either on paper or on the computer.

Motivations and Attitudes

- **Motivations:** Abi uses technologies **to accomplish her tasks.** She learns new technologies if and when she needs to, but prefers to use methods she is **already familiar and comfortable with, to keep her focus** on the tasks she cares about.
- **Computer Self-Efficacy:** Abi has **lower self confidence than her peers about doing unfamiliar computing tasks.** If problems arise with her technology, she often **blames herself for these problems.** This affects whether and how she will persevere with a task if technology problems have arisen.
- **Attitude toward Risk:** Abi's life is a little complicated and she **rarely has spare time.** So she is **risk averse about using unfamiliar technologies that might need her to spend extra time** on them, even if the new features might be relevant. She instead performs tasks using familiar features, because they're more predictable about what she will get from them and how much time they will take.

Attitude to Technology

- **Information Processing Style:** Abi tends towards a comprehensive information processing style when she needs to gather more information. So, instead of acting upon the first option that seems promising, she **gathers information comprehensively to try to form a complete understanding of the problem before trying to solve it.** Thus, her style is "burst-y"; first she reads a lot, then she acts on it in a batch of activity.
- **Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering :** When learning new technology, Abi leans toward **process-oriented learning,** e.g., tutorials, step-by-step processes, wizards, online how-to videos, etc. **She doesn't particularly like learning by tinkering with software** (i.e., just trying out new features or commands to see what they do), but when she does tinker, it has positive effects on her understanding of the software.

¹Abi represents users with motivations/attitudes and information/learning styles similar to hers. For data on people similar to and different from Abi, see <http://gendermag.org/Foundations.html>

Figure-3: Customized Abi persona used in this study. The blue text (background, age, occupation, etc.) are the customizable portions.

